

Challenges in System Level Testing

The purpose of the survey is to understand better the challenges in improving the quality and minimizing the cost of System-Level Testing of 5G systems at Nokia.

The survey consists of 3 parts and should not take more than 10 minutes to finish.

Questions 1 to 17 ask to evaluate the 'Importance', 'Urgency', and 'Difficulty' of the presented challenge.

Question 18 asks about any areas that might have been missed.

Questions 19 and 20 ask about experience and role.

Importance evaluates how much impact would solving the challenge have on process effectiveness.

Urgency evaluates how fast the issue should be addressed.

Difficulty estimates how complex and costly would solving the issue be.

Note: The questionnaire is for research purposes only and is fully anonymous.

* Required

Coverage (1/4)

1. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to focus on **corner-case testing** to ensure high quality? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

2. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to focus on **low occurrence failures** to ensure high quality? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

3. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to focus on **performance testing** to ensure high quality? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

4. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to focus on **customer scenario testing** to ensure high quality? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

5. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to accurately identify and test **hidden feature dependencies**? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

6. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to effectively plan **OTA test scope** to catch OTA-specific defects? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

7. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to effectively catch **HW configuration-specific problems** out of thousands of possible HW configurations? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

8. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to effectively design **exploratory testing** to improve quality with no diminishing returns? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

9. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to define the optimal coverage in **maintenance testing** to ensure high quality? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

10. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to establish the **useful lifetime of a test scenario**? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

11. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to mitigate **regression scope increase** not to endanger quality? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

12. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to find **areas of increased risk** (defect prone) to be tested with more focus? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

13. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to effectively **balance between CRT, CIT, and CDRT** test coverage? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

14. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to build effective **defect prediction models**? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

15. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to secure proper **competence ramp up** of test engineers? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

16. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to accurately **measure test effectiveness**? *

	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

17. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to manage **duplication of effort** between test teams? *

	Very high	Low	Medium	High	Very high	I don't know
Importance	☐					
Urgency	☐					
Difficulty	☐					

18. What **other challenges** do You see in System Level Testing?

19. **How long do You work** in the Software Engineering field? *

- Less than 3 years
- Between 3 and 6 years
- Between 6 and 12 years
- More than 12 years
- I don't want to answer

20. What is **Your current role**? *

- Technical
- Management
- I don't want to answer

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